

A Communicative Competence Model in English Language Undergraduate Program in Cantho University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 08, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 10, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Competence, Communicative, Models, English language</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5771248</p>	<p><i>It is necessary for higher education institutions to equip and train English language students to have the ability to use the language flexibly and effectively in real life and various social situations. The requirement in the current period is that it is necessary to have an appropriate communication competency model so that it can be implemented in the above training programs. In this article, with reference to various communication competency models that have been studied and applied in the world as well as in the context and practical conditions of Vietnam, a model of communication competency in a Vietnamese context was proposed. The communicative competence model consists of four main components which are grammar competence, discourse competence, socio-cultural competence and information and communication technology competence. Hopefully, with the model proposed by the authors, it will make an important contribution to the formation and improvement of communication capacity for English language students, and at the same time meet the output standards of the professional training program. university degree in the current period.</i></p>

Introduction

Since globalization and international integration are the trends of the present times, Vietnam is not an exception. Activities involving exchange and cooperation in the region and internationally in various fields have become increasingly diversified in form and popularity. In this context, the need to teach and learn foreign languages, especially English language, is becoming more and more necessary and important. Recognizing the role and importance of foreign language teaching and learning, in order to be consistent in awareness and action, the Government of Vietnam has issued a series of guidelines and policies, such as decrees and directives to guide, promote and develop effective teaching and learning of English. A big step forward in the above guideline came with Decision No. 1400/QĐ-TTg of the Government issued on September 30, 2008 on the approval of the Project "Teaching and learning foreign languages in the national education system in the period of 2008 - 2020", which stated: "Comprehensively renovating foreign language teaching and learning in the national education system, implementing new foreign language teaching and learning programs at all educational levels and training levels" and "By 2020, the majority of Vietnamese young people graduating from secondary schools, colleges and universities will have sufficient foreign language ability to use independent languages, and be confident in communicating, studying and working in an integrated, multilingual environment. language, multiculturalism; making foreign languages a strength of the Vietnamese people, serving the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country".

Therefore, an appropriate communicative competence model, which can be deployed in teaching and learning, especially for the organization of English language training programs in particular Vietnam is urgent in both theory and practice. Based on various studies, synthesis and inheritance of models that are researched and recognized in the world, the authors proposed a model of language communicative competence in actual conditions in Vietnam, contributing to supporting the theoretical basis for teaching and learning activities of English language programs, meeting the output standards of university-level training programs. In addition, the authors also make some recommendations for management levels, higher education institutions, lecturers and students of English language in order to contribute to improving the efficiency and quality of English language. in the above action..

1. Literature review

2.1 Definitions:

2.1.1 Competence

There are many authors, research works, and different definitions of competence, depending on the industry. According to Hoang Phe's Vietnamese Dictionary (2003) "capability" is understood as "*capability, subjective or natural condition available to perform a certain activity*". Vietnam Encyclopedia (2003) mentioned

"Capability is considered as an individual's characteristic that demonstrates a degree of proficiency, i.e. being able to competently and reliably perform certain types of activities".

The view of the Ministry of Education and Training - the governing body for education and training in Vietnam, says: "Capacity is the ability to successfully carry out activities in a given context through the general mobilization of combination of knowledge, skills, and other personal attributes such as interests, beliefs, and will"

In English, the Concise Oxford Dictionary defines competence as "the ability to perform a job or task". The Cambridge Dictionary defines competence as "the ability to do something well".

According to Gonczi et al. (1990), competence is "Knowledge, abilities, skills and attitudes embodied in the context of a carefully selected set of practical job tasks within the appropriate range".

And in linguistics, Chomsky (1965) - the first author to introduce the concept of "language competence" - to differentiate knowledge of language from behavior is "the actual use of language in a particular situation". It is undeniable that Chomsky's theory of language was influential but also controversial and this led to other theories, including the theory of communicative competence.

2.1.2 Communicative competence

According to Chomsky (1965), basically, learning a language, with the ultimate, most important purpose, is to use it for communication purposes. This is a new point and different from other linguists in terms of views and models of communicative competence, Chomsky was the first to separate grammatical knowledge from knowledge required to communicate. According to the author, the ability to communicate in English can be conceptualized as "the ability to apply grammatical knowledge and social knowledge to know how to make sentences in English appropriate to the context".

2.2 Important Communicative Competence Models

Many models of communicative competence have been used by higher education institutions around the world with the aim of helping learners have the ability to receive and use language appropriately and effectively in many other social situations together. The history of forming the modern communicative competence model began with Chomsky in the 60s of the 20th century and followed by the construction and development studies of a plethora of linguists. It is vital to mention reputable linguists, with prominent names in the research and development of communication competency models, from Hymes, Canales to Celce-Mercia and colleagues.

2.2.1 Hymes' Model

Hymes (1972) introduced the term "communicative competence" by which language users need to master grammar rules and apply them effectively in social communication. Hymes used the word "form" to refer to grammatically correct sentences, "feasible" to refer to the psychological factors affecting speech formation, and "appropriate" to refer to the use of appropriate language in a specific context.

Hymes divided communication competence into two distinct components: Knowledge and Ability for use. The first element, Knowledge, consisted of four elements. One is the grammatical factor (what is possible); which means the ability to express ideas with the correct sentence structure according to the grammar. The second element was what is feasible; that is whether the speaker is influenced by factors such as psychological barriers, limited memory or not. Third, the appropriateness factor; that is, the statement must be true and acceptable according to the circumstances. Fourth, the behavioral element; that is, the speaker completes the statement. The second component is Usability, which consists of three factors: motivation, influencing factors, and interoperability. These three factors can be considered as psychological factors that have a decisive impact on whether the speaker can use the language even though the speaker has good grammar knowledge and wishes to communicate.

Hymes' theory were accepted by many linguists, including Widdowson (1978), who viewed language learning as a process not only to learn knowledge of grammar rules but to gain the ability to use use language to communicate. On this point, Widdowson was influenced by Hymes on the concept of learning languages and using them appropriately in social communication.

2.2.2 Munby's Model

Munby (1978) proposed three factors as the foundation of communication competence. First, the socio-cultural orientation, which was understanding and using the correct sentence structure in the respective social situation. Second, it was social semantics. The last factor was discursive activity, i.e. the ability to use linguistic form to communicate.

Munby was the first to make the sociocultural factor a factor. According to Munby, knowledge of language such as grammar and sentence structure is not enough for effective communication. Therefore, the speaker needed to know the types of sentences or ways of saying that were suitable for a specific social context. It was clear here

that Munby was influenced by Hymes on the element of "appropriateness", the use of appropriate language in a particular context as mentioned above.

The second factor, social semantics, concerned which language speakers chose to express what they wanted to say. This idea was somewhat similar to Halliday when Halliday argued that the ability to produce speech was a process where the speaker first had an idea and then said it out.

2.2.3 Halliday's Model

Halliday (1979) focused on language functions and proposed 7 major language functions for communication purposes. One was the instrumental function (Instrumental), where language was seen as a tool to satisfy the speaker's needs (similar to the need for food or water). The second was the control function (Regulatory) such as commanding, persuading, etc. The third function was the interactive function (Interactional), in which language had the nature of social communication. Fourth, it was personal function, whereby language was used to express personal opinions and ego of the speaker. Fifth, it was the exchange function (Representational). Speakers used language to exchange and receive information. Sixth, that was the discovery function (Heuristic). Speakers used language to learn and explore the world around them through questioning. Finally, that was the imaginative function. Activities such as describing, telling, and imagining were some of the common examples of this function.

In Halliday's view, what was important to a speaker was that the capacity for meaning could materialize the behavioral ability (actuable) and lead to lexical grammatical ability (speakable).

2.2.4 Canale and Swain's Model

Canale and Swain (1980) shared the same opinion as Hymes, criticizing Chomsky's concept in making a clear distinction between the two components of knowledge and competence. However, unlike Hymes, these authors did not include Ability for use in communication capabilities.

In addition, the two authors also supported Munby's (1978) point of view that grammar and communication skills should not be separated.

Canale and Swain (1980) proposed three components of communicative competence: Grammatical competence refers to language knowledge and the ability to use correct grammatical structures in communication; Social competence is the ability to understand and produce appropriate statements in different social contexts; Strategic competence is the ability to recognize and correct communication breakdowns and to use verbal or gestural strategies to improve communication effectiveness. Canale (1983) also added a fourth component, discourse competence, i.e. the ability to combine grammatical structures and meanings to achieve a harmonious spoken or written text due to its associative and coherent.

2.2.5 Bachman's Model

Bachman (1990) then together with Palmer (1996) developed a more detailed model of Canale and Swain. The authors divided language competence into two main components: Linguistic knowledge (including grammatical knowledge and textual knowledge) and Pragmatic knowledge (including functional knowledge and socio-linguistic knowledge). In terms of nature, the textual knowledge corresponded to the discourse knowledge of Canale and Swain. Regarding pragmatic knowledge, because it included functional knowledge, it could be considered as the successor to Halliday's linguistic functions as mentioned. Bachman's sociolinguistic knowledge was very similar to the social competence of Canale and Swain because, according to Bachman, speakers exercised linguistic functions in a manner appropriate to the context.

Bachman and Palmer's strategic competencies were linguistic knowledge combined with metacognitive strategies that enabled learners to set goals, evaluate sources of communication, and plan.

However, unlike Canale and Swain, Bachman believed that strategic competence should not be at the same level as grammatical competence, but should be at the same level as linguistic competence because, according to the author, strategic competence was a very important part involving the entire use of communicative language.

2.2.6 Model of Celce-Mercia et al

The model of Celce-Mercia, Dornyei and Thurrel (1995) included 5 components: Linguistic competence; Ability to use strategy; Socio-cultural competence; Performance competence and Discourse competence. Here, we could clearly see the inheritance and development of the competence model of Canale and Swain. The authors developed Canale and Swain's discourse competence into sociolinguistic competence. From this, the socio-linguistic capacity developed into two capacities, including socio-cultural competence and performance capacity.

Celce-Mercia et al used the phrase "linguistic competence" rather than "grammatical competence" like Canale and Swain. "Linguistic competence" refers to knowledge of syntax, grammar, phonetics and vocabulary, while "sociocultural competence" was a necessary condition to speak and receive messages in the true sense of the socio-cultural context.

2.2.7 Usó-Juan and Martínez-Flor's Model

The more recent communicative model of Usó-Juan and Martínez-Flor (2006) included Linguistic competence; Pragmatic competence; Intercultural Competency and Strategic Competence. This is the only model of communicative competence that considered “intercultural competence” as a major component showing the correlation between learner culture and target language culture.

Sociocultural competence is commonly understood as the ability to use country-specific information, understanding and communication technology to achieve mutual understanding with people from other cultures. Therefore, Usó-Juan and Martínez-Flor's intercultural competence could be viewed as an extension rather than a new element in the model of communicative competence.

3. Research Method

3.1 Research questions

This study was aimed to find out an appropriate model of communicative competence; therefore, two questions were raised in this study:

1. What is an appropriate model of communicative competence for undergraduate students of English language in a Vietnamese context?
2. What are the perceptions of students and teachers towards this suggested model?

3.2 Participants

This study involved 213 undergraduate students in the School of Foreign Languages in Cantho University. They were following various courses in the English Language program.

3.3 Research design

This research was of descriptive and qualitative nature. The previous models of communicative competence showed some signs of effectiveness. However, they began to reveal some weaknesses as students were not fully equipped with much needed competences. The authors used common models of communicative competence in this study and then proposed an adapted model to be used in a Vietnamese context of higher education.

4. Findings

4.1 A new requirement in communicative competence

The 4.0 industrial revolution, the combination of technology and artificial intelligence (AI), has created challenges and development opportunities for many fields, including education and training. In order to survive and adapt to that great change, people, in addition to regularly updated and supplemented knowledge, also need to have cross-cultural understanding and soft skills ...

Globalization and international integration lead to the need for communication, connection and cooperation within the region and internationally.

English language has been and is considered to be the most commonly used language in the world in the current period, with more than 60 countries using English as the main language - mother tongue and nearly 100 countries using it. English is a second language, so it can be said that English is the language of global transactions and communication. Teaching and learning English well can be considered the key to opening the door to success. To expand and contact the outside world, update human knowledge, requires a solid English foundation to communicate well.

In the age of information technology (IT), the role of the Internet cannot be denied. This is also established and recognized in UNESCO's Leveraging ICT to achieve Education 2030, with the above framework stating the importance, educational goals and promoting IT usability by 2030. , whereby understanding and usability are an integral component of modern communication.

According to UNESCO (2008), information and communication technology competence refers to the knowledge, skills and ability to use IT for the purpose of collecting, processing and preparing information to support activities between individuals and groups to study and work.

Thus, in this study, IT and Communication Competency is defined as: “Knowledge, skills, and ability to use information technology for the purpose of communicating through written or audio-visual media with effective results by network connection”.

4.2. The suggested model of communicative competence in Cantho University

This model of communication Competence in English Language Training was proposed on the basis of inheriting models published and recognized by research linguists in the world in the global context, the development of science and technology and Vietnam's conditions. The authors paid attention to three key components: Grammatical competence; Sociolinguistic competence and Discourse competence. At the same

time, a new component is added, which is Information and communication technology competence, in which information and communication technology capacity is the ability to use media to express, store and propagate in the media. communicate.

Therefore, the proposed Model of English Language Communication Competency could be summarized in the following diagram (Fig. 1):

In support of the above activity, the current reality is that electronic devices such as Ipad, smartphones, computers and the Internet have gradually become familiar and are an indispensable component in life and learning and work... Although it is considered a virtual world, the interactions in it are real because users have real communication needs. This model is necessary and highly feasible because it takes advantage of the advantages and achievements of science and technology in developing English language communication capacity for learners.

5. Conclusion

The impacts of the times such as globalization and international integration, the industrial revolution 4.0 with connected things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI) have posed a lot of challenges as well as opportunities in the world and in all fields, including teaching and learning languages, especially English at higher education institutions. Developing communication capacity is an important and mandatory requirement upon graduation and graduation for every English language major student. It is also an extremely important capacity to help them continue to study or acquire lifelong practice. The application of information technology and communication in teaching and learning English is not very new, but higher education institutions need to pay attention to creating an environment, conditions and organization for teaching staff and students to continue studying.

Combining traditional and modern methods - using IT and media to diversify information and communication channels - contributes to the development of essential competencies, bridging the gap to academic success. In order for this activity to really become a trend and promote the strengths of higher education institutions in Vietnam, it is necessary to have the coordination, support and active participation of stakeholders.

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